

BASIC CRITERIA OF THE ART OF VOCAL MUSIC.

Ibrakhimov Azizbek Ismonjon ugli

Student of namangan state university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7634229>

Annotation: This article provides detailed information about the reforms in the field of art, music, culture, vocal music, opera genre, the main parts of the opera genre, such as breath, voice, articulation, diction, rezanato.

Keywords: opera, culture, tradition, vocal art, opera, breath, sound, voice, singer, hearing, performance, mouth, music, vocal, resonators, articulation.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston Respublikasidagi san'at, musiqa, madaniyat, sohasidagi islohotlar, vokal musiqa san'ati opera janri, opera janrining nafas, ovoz, artikulyatsiya, diksiya, rezanato kabi asosiy qismlari haqida batafsil ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: opera, madaniyat, an'ana, vokal san'ati, opera, nafas, tovush, ovoz, xonanda, eshitish, ijro, og'iz, musiqa, vokal, rezanatorlar, artikulyatsiya.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена подробная информация о реформах в области искусства, музыки, культуры, вокальной музыки, жанра оперы, основных частях оперного жанра, таких как дыхание, голос, артикуляция, дикция, резанато.

Ключевые слова: опера, культура, традиция, вокальное искусство, опера, дыхание, звук, голос, певец, слух, исполнение, уста, музыка, вокал, резонаторы, артикуляция.

Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts[1]. In particular, in May 30, 2019 “ On the organization of the activities of the state museum-reserves Sarmishsay”, “Shakhrisabz”, “Termez” and “Kokand” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 443 of April 21 [2] , 2020 “On measures to further increase the efficiency of the fine and applied arts” Resolution No. PD - 4688 of May 26, 2020 “Culture Decree No. PD-6000 of May 23 [3], Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures to further increase the efficiency of the field of fine and applied arts” dated April 21, 2020 No. PD-4688, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On additional measures related to supporting the entrepreneurial activity and employment of young people, their social protection and meaningful organization of their free time” 20th of 2021 Decree No. PD-6208 of April. It is known that the 20th century was a period of sharp changes in the art of Uzbek music, “unconventional” compositional creativity and new forms of concerts

appeared. In this regard, the concept of “variety” entered our circulation in musical culture.

The art of vocal music is one of the main parts of the opera genre. Directly, this art form is the main pillar for singers. This art form consists of a number of main parts. These are: breath, voice, articulation, diction, resonator, etc. The main goal of this science is to acquire the theoretical knowledge of modern vocal science and to form the ability to sing modern vocal songs. The purpose of vocal music is to cultivate the aesthetic and artistic taste of future music students, to develop the skills of singing in a professional style. Particular attention should be paid to the technical development of the sound apparatus, the formation of artistic skills, and education at the artistic level. The structure and movement of the sound paths in vocal music singing, its types of voice production, knowing the signs of singing breath, articulation, intonation and dynamics, breathing. There are other types of ani below. Now let's stop for breath. We can take as an example three different breathing methods. These are “with a head”, “with a chest”, “with a chest and a belly”. The shoulder of a person is raised (swayed) in the sarpard type. In Sarpar, this appearance means that the air passes only through the upper part of the lungs without moving the chest at all. This breathing does not correspond to the performance at all. The performer must breathe in such a way that the chest is filled with air, the shoulders should be calm, and the height should be correct. In order to breathe, the ribs make up the chest.[4]

The heart and lungs are located in it. When the lungs are filled with air (inhalation), they have a large volume and push the ribs to both sides. These are rib and chest breathing. After breathing, we will focus on another main part of the vocal.

This “Resonator” dies when approximately 80% of the human’s sound energy passes through the surrounding tissue. Their vibration will be wasted. In the air gap above and below the fold, the sound resistance undergoes acoustic changes and increases, so these spaces are called resonators. Resonators are divided into two. These are divided into upper and chest resonators, oral and nasal cavities, and head resonators. And in this regard, it should be said that the voice plays an important role in vocal performance. The location of the larynx in performance should be neither low nor high, it is individual “Individually” for each performer, it depends on how his vocal apparatus is structured. The larynx is an organ that occurs for the production of sound. It is directly related to the vocal apparatus. All the organs that make up the voice make up the vocal apparatus. It includes

the larynx, vocal tubes, throat, trachea, bronchi, lungs, chest, respiratory muscles, diaphragm and abdominal muscles. Articulating equipment is also necessary. It should be clear in our words and in our pronunciation. That is, it should be loud and expressive enough to be heard by those sitting at the end of the hall, I think this phrase is very important for us. It is very important to have good diction. It is necessary to pronounce the sentences clearly and clearly. I think it is very necessary to further research on the articulatory apparatus and develop its technical capabilities in order to achieve good results. "Diction" is the accurate pronunciation of sounds and words. When singing, it is very important that the deviation is free and aesthetic. [5]

It is also an integral part of the tongue, jaw and lips; beautiful opening of the mouth during performance helps to place the tongue, larynx, and throat correctly and to set the entire vocal apparatus correctly. As we can see, the field of "Vocal" is one of the most complex fields. All the organs necessary for the vocal field are inextricably linked with each other. In the earlier period of the development of the art of vocal singing, the description of voices came first. These are two types of "Male" and two types of "Female" voices. These divisions have continued to this day. A professional singer's voice should have a two-octave range and even tension throughout the entire range. Voices differ in timbre and pitch. "Women's" voice: "Soprano", "Messo soprano", "Alt".

There are types of "men's" voice: "tenor", "baritone", "bass". In these types, singers choose their own ages, determining the range of their voices. Vocal music forms are also different. It requires creative tension from listeners. Among the monumental classical compositions for soloists, choir and orchestra: oratorios of Mozart, Handel and Bach, requiems of Berlioz, Verdi, cantatas of Tanev, Rachmaninoff and Prokofiev. Their musical content is not limited to the usual song motifs. [6] They contain complex choral polyphony, solo arias, and extended symphonic pieces. In order to understand the music of these classic compositions, one must have the necessary aesthetic experience to fully grasp their grand scale. When we listen to a song, a romance, an aria, we first of all enjoy the beauty of a melody inspired by a poetic word. Another important criterion for the artistic quality of such music is how faithfully the ideas and images of poetry are embodied in it.

References:

1. Mirkhakimova Feruza Kholdorjon kizi. Activity of Mutal Burkhanov House Museum. CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HISTORY VOLUME 03 ISSUE: 11 | NOV 2022 (ISSN: 2660-6836). 76-81 pp.

2. Topildiev Odiljon Rakhimjonovich, Mirkhakimova Feruza Kholdorjon kizi. REFORM IN THE FIELD OF CULTURE AND ART IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. Web of scientist: International scientific research journal. ISSN: 2776-0979, Volume 3, Issue 5, May., 2022.196-198 pp.
3. Mirhakimova, F. K. (2021). The state museum of history and culture of Namangan region past and today. Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research, 10(8), 84-89.
4. Jabbarov A. Musical drama and comedy genres in the creativity of Uzbek composers. Tashkent, "G'. Ghulom", 2000. -P.21
5. Hamidov H. History of Uzbek traditional singing culture. Tashkent, "Teacher", 1996.-P.40
- P. Odilov A. History of performance on Uzbek folk instruments. Tashkent, "Teacher", 1995. -P.30.

